

Pollinators: Facilitating Collaboration Across Tech Central

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Definition and Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

For the past decade, attention and research have focused on the role of new businesses in generating employment, fostering innovation, and increasing the productiveness of a geographical region. In this context, a link between the incorporation of new organizations and the development of an area is anticipated (Flores & Kovács, 2018).

The evolution of the entrepreneurship ecosystem can be traced in the United States. The application of the terminology 'ecosystem' to entrepreneurial activity has been linked with the Silicon Valley development. The location of the Silicon Valley involves a geographical area where the combination of universities, entrepreneurs, and venture capitalists produced pioneering organizations (Flores & Kovács, 2018).

For fifty years, the entrepreneurship ecosystem has been growing and organizing a physical space and business whereby such firms have been deployed. Most studies have concentrated on the factors that led to the success of Silicon Valley. The Silicon Valley is considered as the greatest competitive advantages around the world built on the integrated action of an organized economic structure between the academic institutions and industry, flexible work, sources of capital with experience, and network and media prepared to spread the success story of an important mass of entrepreneurs staying in a certain geographical region (Flores & Kovács, 2018).

The entrepreneurial terminology system (EE) as a notion did not appear till 1990. However, the concept of the development of enterprises in a specified region is common. Also, it is renowned that is a network that backs up the development of entrepreneurship and contemplates the distinct types of policies, institutions, or investors. The entrepreneurship ecosystem as a notion was defined by Moore as a space of interconnection and mutual reliance between the economic agents whose communal health was vital for the success and survival of firms (Flores & Kovács, 2018).

In the previous twenty years, many authors have come forward to give their opinions on the descriptions of the entrepreneurship ecosystem. Mason & Brown (2014) defined an entrepreneurship ecosystem as the set of factors, actors, and processes interconnected in a specified geographical area. These factors connect formally to arbitrary and regulate the local entrepreneurial setting to enable innovation and, thus, the growth of businesses (Mason & Brown, 2014). According to Stam & Spigel (2016), the entrepreneurship ecosystem is the set of interdependent actors and factors coordinated in a manner that allow entrepreneurship in a productive manner in a certain area (Stam & Spigel, 2016). Furthermore, Flores & Kovács (2018) argued that the entrepreneurship ecosystem stresses on the interdependence between actors and aspects though observe entrepreneurship as the final output of the ecosystem (Flores & Kovács, 2018). The entrepreneurial ecosystem is the community that constitutes the many aspects independent from one another, which liaise with themselves in a geographical region and evolve. The development of new businesses is facilitated by the entrepreneurial system (Flores & Kovács, 2018). Therefore, the foundation of the entrepreneurship ecosystem is its people and trust and collaboration that enables them to interact peacefully. Hence, an entrepreneurial system is an ecosystem that enables the quick flow of information and resources that assists entrepreneurs in finding the thing they require at every phase of growth.

2 TechCentral

Tech Central was announced in 2018 as a future centre for innovation located in the heart of Sydney, in an area surrounding Sydney Central Station. Tech Central has a proposed 24-hectare area in the city centre, bordered by Pitt Street, Cleveland Street, Eddy Avenue and Elizabeth Street (Central Precinct -, n.d.; Talevski, 2018).

Tech Central is a joint proposal between the NSW Government, Atlassian, Fishburners and Tech Sydney. The NSW Government established an advisory board after the announcement that included the chair of Jobs for NSW, David Thodey, members from Sydney Business Chamber, University of Sydney, University of Technology Sydney, and other industry experts from various Australian start-ups (A New Vision for Sydney's Tech Precinct | University of Technology Sydney, 2018; Talevski, 2018).

In 2020 there was a series of events that helped promote Tech Central's future through its development phase. The NSW Government pledged to supply \$48.2 million in funding to Tech Central (Talevski, 2020). At the same time, Dexu & Frasers, two-property development, and management companies, formed a partnership to develop a twin office building in Tech Central designed by an international team and projected to cost \$2.5 billion (Tech Central Reaches Higher with \$2.5 Billion Towers | Dexu, n.d.).

In April 2021, NTT pledged to join Tech Central and establish a Cyber Security Centre of Excellence. NTT also pledged to launch CyRise cybersecurity boot camp programs through NSW (Spencer, 2021).

Tech Central was proposed as a space to bring together start-ups, scale-ups, and other components of the innovation sector to help technology grow in NSW (Central Precinct -, n.d.). While it is still in the early stages with planning it is beginning to change things in Sydney City, the most obvious is the ability for new buildings to reach up to 42 stories tall (Central Precinct -, n.d.). This is being embraced by Atlassian and the Dexu & Frasers buildings which will reach new heights in the Sydney skyline as well as promote sustainability and health in their design (Project in Focus: Sydney's Central Precinct, n.d.). It is likely that these changes and the early anchor companies will be a great benefit to Tech Central's future in attracting a wide variety of industries to join as buildings progress in the area.

For Tech Central to succeed as an Entrepreneurial Ecosystem it needs to establish a diverse community of stakeholders that interact in ways that allow the area to grow and draw in new companies. Ideally stakeholders would come from a diverse range of backgrounds to allow for collaboration so they can cross-pollinate ideas and projects, from the creative industries to medical research and beyond. These early stages make it hard to see this happening, however the anchor companies that are present are drawing in more, e.g., NTT signing on, Dexu & Frasers planning a joint building. These larger parent companies will also bring in associations with smaller companies that are held under their corporate umbrella, which will hopefully continue to attract new stakeholders which will continue to feed into creating a self-sustaining ecosystem that continues to grow and thrive for decades to come. This is further enhanced by NTT planning its CyRise bootcamps in other regions of NSW to help raise awareness and connections throughout the state and potentially across Australia.

3 Ecosystem Map

Our ecosystem map identifies who we believe are key stakeholders within our chosen ecosystem, Tech Central. We have organised these stakeholders into their respective industry and separated them by colour to highlight the business itself, and the key member within that business. This allows a viewer to easily navigate which category each stakeholder belongs to, along with their connections within the ecosystem. We utilised dotted lines to symbolise indirect links and unbroken lines to signify direct links, allowing for those who are directly involved with Tech Central to be identified. It became evident that this map coincided with the feedback from industry professionals who explained that there are missing connections between stakeholders as there is a sense of competition. In addition, by viewing the ecosystem from a broad lens, rather than focusing on an individual industry, we are able to understand the complexity of the interactions that occur within.

4 Leverage Proposal

4.1 (Big) Why and What

We propose a vision for the entrepreneurship ecosystem in Tech Central Sydney over the next decade, by establishing a media company named Pollinators. The name encompasses our view of the ecosystem as a beehive, in which everyone's contribution is essential to reach a common goal. Pollinators will establish connections between stakeholders to offer a supportive environment occupied with people driven by the ambition to urge action.

Our research and interviews noted that competition is a limitation of growth. Interviewees highlighted gaps within Tech Central such as competition and lack of diversity. It became clear that although Tech Central aims to provide opportunities of collaboration between stakeholders, the environment is still built upon competition. Our vision is for Pollinators to foster collaboration and remove the competitive barriers associated with industry. Start-ups and enterprises can collaborate with each other and major stakeholders to share resources and skills. They will also be given the opportunity to interact with the market through networking. Moreover, sustainability cannot be ignored by Tech Central and its stakeholders which is a long-term goal in future development of the Tech precinct.

We have chosen to provide visualisations of the type of media we believe will be a key instrument for driving change within Tech Central. It is through social media in which most consumers and stakeholders receive and share information, therefore by creating campaigns which highlight the many features of Sydney's Technology Precinct, we believe this will drive collaboration and diversity.

5 Who, How & When?

Our vision for the future of the ecosystem will be facilitated by levers and activators who will allow connections between various stakeholders. The key levers are advertising, social media, networking events and marketing. These levers will play an instrumental role in the ecosystem by it fostering communication between firms and consumers. In addition, the use of technology will allow a wide target audience to be reached which will encourage stakeholders from outside the ecosystem to be involved. It also enables the business to receive feedback from the market which, in our interviews, we identified is essential for development. It can be used when establishing virtual workspaces where the workers can liaise and develop ideas. With the availability of technology, it is easy for businesses to reach millions of individuals around the world with just a click of a button (Elia et al., 2020). Web-based advertising constitutes social media, including blogs and social networking sites as well as media. The websites can be built using WordPress. Social media accounts are easy to build for businesses and offer exposure on a diversity of platforms. networking events will allow the entrepreneurs to socialize with the other people in the same field who might have more years of business experience. These networking events will be instrumental to the entrepreneurs because it will equip them with knowledge to run the startups despite the hurdles that will come along the way. Apart from this, social media is a lever in Tech Central Sydney because it will allow the startups to socialize with the consumers. The social media managers in collaboration with the marketing team will get acquainted of the necessary improvements to be made on the product as well as the products that the consumers need in the market. Thus, these levels will lead to improvement for change in the Tech Central Sydney.

Some key activators that can leverage development are City of Sydney, NSW Government, universities, UTS startups, USYD Incubate, and Atlassian. The first layer of activators would be from the City of Sydney and the NSW Government. We believe that through partnering with these stakeholders early Pollinators would have a stable funding and wide-reaching pool of advisors to help establish clear goals to promote Tech Central. This early intervention will also allow Pollinators to establish contact with new stakeholders as they pledge to be involved with Tech Central allowing for easy connections. These connections will then lead to clearer promotion of the sector and openness about collaboration with other stakeholders in the future.

Atlassian will be a key activator in the Tech Central Sydney. The local technology giant, Atlassian, has dedicated itself to become an anchor tenant of the Tech Central Precinct. Atlassian which is a renowned software development company with small, medium, and established enterprises as its clients will attract clients who will purchase services from the precinct. This wealth of experience as well as the planned HQ establish the importance for engagement between Atlassian and Pollinators. In ideal circumstances Pollinators would rent office space in Atlassian to establish a physical presence within Tech Central, not only for production, but also to allow easier facilitation of networking events and conferences. We believe that the visibility this would provide would be crucial to the success of Pollinators and allow it to grow with Tech Central over time.

UTS and USYD will be vital to leverage development in the entrepreneurship ecosystem because they will offer a platform for the students to carry out research using the latest tools and technology. Due to their proximity to Tech Central and Central Station, students would be exposed to the projects and corporations through advertising, events, networking, and internships. Having this exposure as well as working relationships with the Universities would encourage collaboration to drive future developments and long-term relationships on multiple levels. UTS start-ups and USYD Incubate will also act as activators in the Tech Central Sydney because they will leverage the technology to offer bespoke services for its clients. The startups will deliver products and services to the clients including web development, SAAS, and web hosting services. These services can be fed by Pollinators to network these small-scale start-ups with larger entities to foster collaboration and mentorships into the future, even access the ideas presented by students to help feed into the Tech Central Ecosystem via promotion.

We propose that Pollinators establish in time for the opening of Atlassian's HQ, to be involved with publicity of events and facilitating early interaction in the ecosystem. Having an early presence and connections with the staff as they onboard to new sites, would be the most beneficial way to foster a sense of community. The more of the ecosystem they can observe directly, the greater the ability to promote ideas and create networks between groups that otherwise, may not interact. Pollinators would function best with a holistic view of the precinct and ecosystem, to reduce fear of competition and foster a sense of community collaboration that feeds back into Tech Central.

5.1 Future Map

This visualisation highlights our definition of the transformation that will take place within the ecosystem. We have included the addition of new start-ups such as Minderoo, in order to attract those outside of the geographic area such as indigenous, women and rural entrepreneurs. In addition, we have included further interactions amongst stakeholders who we believe, through social, networking events and social media, will be given opportunities to interact as previously hindered by funding and resource limitations.

6 Value to the stakeholders

Pollinators will increase collaboration, diversity, understanding of what the other parts of the ecosystem do and knowing how to access them.

Universities - students have access to internships, learn more about possible jobs and learn practical skills to operate a business.

Industry Agents - more research is done in their field, more funding in their area, push for policy changes to enable more opportunities for innovation.

(Sarah Glennan from the GSC says "Policy is not in place forever, it can change, this happens most often when industry pushes for it.")

Startup founders - knowledge of professional services, getting recognised by more developed companies, access to research, access to a market, creating a larger network and discovering the most appropriate funding options.

City of Sydney - more jobs created and higher quality of living in its council area. Infrastructure improvement including public transport and green spaces. More visibility

worldwide, associated with internationally renowned innovation developed in Sydney and resulting in attracting more talent.

Fishburners – gets to see products that are not under their umbrella, things they could be associated with, and learning about the technologies of the

startups in Tech Central. Brings more people into the area for events, help build nationwide, and global network associated with the City of Sydney.

Atlassian – the startups they host are using the newest technology to hit the market which they can adopt for use in their company. Their building will be filled with tenants.

UTS startups – Help a diverse group of students see wider opportunities than before. Naturally create interaction with students, creating an increased range of mentors. Understanding

how the other stakeholders can be of benefit to them.

Local Business – more employment, new infrastructure, better locations, hotels guest numbers for conferences and events. More financial stability because of the foot traffic.

Professional services – more business, ability to get feedback from startups on how to improve to take their business ideas internationally

Marginalised groups – supporting communities that haven't been represented in the entrepreneurial scene like women, Indigenous Peoples, LGBTQIA+ community, dis/abilities and immigrants.

Developed business like Westpac Optus and Microsoft can stay relevant with the technology, attract talent by interacting within Pollinators.

Federal government – 'With the Australian economy dominated by natural resources it is important to diversify the economy' Neville. With Pollinators, Tech Central will become an Australian attraction enticing talent worldwide and this will subsequently support the economy.

6.1 Thinking Critically About our Proposal

Negatives:

- Stakeholders may be too busy to get involved.
- Companies' gatekeeping due to fear of competition or imitation (John-Paul Daneel said 'High competition and product relevancy keep the pressure on start-ups to ensure time-to-market is kept to a minimum.')

Some barriers to overcome with our proposal would be:

- Gaining momentum initially
- Funding

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